

MARIO RESTA
DISSEMINATION AND OUTREACH

1. PERSONAL INFORMATIONS

Home Address: Vico I Via Sottotenente Magrone 5, 70054 Giovinazzo (BA), ITALY

Office Address: Dipartimento di Ricerca e Innovazione Umanistica, Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, Strada Torretta s.n., 70122 Bari, ITALY

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6809-0215>

E-mail: mario.resta@uniba.it; resta.mario@gmail.com

Nationality: Italian

Birth Date: 6th June 1987

2. CONFERENCE ORGANISATION AND PARTICIPATION

- 2.1. **2025:** 27th September, **Bertinoro (FC), Italy: scientific coordination** (together with Maria Dell'Isola) of the **unit** on «**Gender Issues in Early Christianity**» of the **11th International Annual Meeting on Christian Origins** [Bertinoro (FC), 25th – 27th September 2025], organised by Mara Rescio, Emiliano Rubens Urciuoli (Centro Italiano di Studi Superiori delle Religioni = CISSR);
- 2.2. **2024:** 3rd October, **Bertinoro (FC), Italy: scientific coordination** (together with Maria Dell'Isola) of the **unit** on «**Women in Early Christianity**» of the **10th International Annual Meeting on Christian Origins** [Bertinoro (FC), 3rd-5th October 2024], organised by Mara Rescio, Emiliano Rubens Urciuoli (CISSR);
- 2.3. **2024:** 17th-18th September, **Monte Sant'Angelo (FG): member of the staff (organising committee)** of the **International Meeting on “*Compilationes francescane: parola, musica e immagine*”**, organised by Immacolata Aulisa, Nunzio Bianchi and Filippo Sedda;
- 2.4. **2024:** 14th May, **Bari: member of the organising committee** of the **Meeting on “60 anni della rivista *Vetera Christianorum* 1964-2023. Ricerche, studi e prospettive”** of the Department of Research and Innovation In Humanities of University of Bari Aldo Moro;
- 2.5. **2023:** 21st September, **Bertinoro (FC), Italy: scientific coordination** (together with Maria Dell'Isola) of the **unit** on «**Women in Early Christianity**» of the **9th International Annual Meeting on Christian Origins** [Bertinoro (FC), 21st – 23rd September 2023], organised by Mara Rescio, Emiliano Rubens Urciuoli (CISSR);
- 2.6. **2022:** 15th September, **Bertinoro (FC), Italy: scientific coordination** (together with Maria Dell'Isola) of the **unit** on «**Women in Early Christianity**» of the **8th International Annual**

Meeting on Christian Origins [Bertinoro (FC), 15th – 17th September 2022], organised by Mara Rescio, Emiliano Rubens Urciuoli (CISSR);

- 2.7. **2022**: 22nd June, **Bologna, Italy**: **chair** of the panel (part I) on «Joy Denied, Joy Rediscovered: Notes on the Legitimacy of Joy from Classical Greek Literature to Byzantine Christianity» of the **Annual Conference** (5th edition) of the **European Accademy of Religion (EuARe)** on «Religion and Diversity» (Bologna, 20th – 23rd June 2022);
- 2.8. **2022**: 14th June, **Matera, Italy**: **discussant** of the panel on «Il Maligno, possessioni e posseduti nel Mezzogiorno medievale» of the *II Convegno della medievistica italiana* (Matera, 13th – 16th June 2022), organised by Società Italiana degli Storici Medievisti (SISMED);
- 2.9. **2021**: 3rd – 5th November, **Bari, Italy**: **member of the staff (organising committee)** of the **International Meeting on “Heretic Jews / Judaizing Heretics. The Construction of Christian Orthodoxy and Anti-Jewish Polemics in Late Antiquity and Early Middle Age”**, organised by Immacolata Aulisa and Claudio Schiano;
- 2.10. **2021**: 29th September, **Bertinoro (FC), Italy**: **scientific coordination** (together with Maria Dell’Isola) of the **unit** on «Women in Early Christianity» of the **7th International Annual Meeting on Christian Origins – online edition** (Bertinoro, 29th September – 2nd October 2021), organised by Mauro Pesce, Mara Rescio, Emiliano Rubens Urciuoli (CISSR);
- 2.11. **2021**: 13th – 16th September, **Santa Maria di Leuca (LE), Italy**: **member of organising committee** of the **International Meeting on “Fede, cultura e pellegrinaggi tra Atlantico e Mediterraneo. Da Finisterre a Santa Maria di Leuca de finibus terrae”**;
- 2.12. **2021**: 6th May, **Santa Maria Capua Vetere (CE), Italy**: **scientific coordination** (together with Antonio Salvati) of the **panel discussion** on «Immagini di santità: “tuttiSanti” e “Futuro Arcaico”» of the **Seminar Series “I santi internauti”**, University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”, Santa Maria Capua Vetere (CE) 8th April – 27th May 2021; link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uIz4-tprHtE&list=PLkv7cijk68iWhmDW9_SSA6nQV1kh-p5IE&index=4;
- 2.13. **2019**: 4th – 5th October, **Monte Sant’Angelo (FG), Italy**: **scientific coordination and member of organising committee** of the **II Incontro Culturale Numismatico “In Sanctorum Nummis Effigies”**, organised by Giuseppe Ruotolo and Domenico Luciano Moretti;

3. LECTURES AT CONFERENCES AND SYMPOSIA

- 3.1. **2025**: 27th September, **Bertinoro (FC), Italy**: «Eunuchs in Late Antiquity: Gender Perspectives Starting from the First Council of Nicaea», **11th International Annual Meeting on Christian Origins** (Bertinoro, 25th – 27th September 2025), organised by Mara Rescio, Emiliano Rubens Urciuoli (CISSR);
- 3.2. **2025**: 23rd September, **Bari**: «La proprietà da privata a divina: la legislazione canonica di Gallia, Spagna e *Africa Proconsularis* (IV-VI secolo)», **International Meeting on “Giorgio**

Otranto, l'Università e il territorio”, organised by Department of Research and Innovation in Humanities of University of Bari Aldo Moro (23rd – 24th September 2025);

- 3.3. **2025:** 18th September, **Milano:** «Uno studio di genere a partire dal I concilio di Nicea: il caso degli eunuchi nella tarda antichità», **Annual Meeting of Consulta Universitaria per la Storia del Cristianesimo e delle Chiese on “Nicea 325. Il concilio e le ricezioni dall’antichità alla contemporaneità”**, Vita-Salute San Raffaele University, 18th – 19th September 2025;
- 3.4. **2024:** 14th November, **Firenze:** «Origini cristiane dell’acquisto della salvezza: la legislazione canonica di Gallia, Spagna e Africa Proconsularis (IV-VI secolo)» for the **II Winter School di Studi sulla Riforma**, Firenze 13th– 17th November 2024;
- 3.5. **2024:** 6th September, **Genzano di Roma (RM):** conference with Rossana Barcellona on the book of R. Barcellona, *Nascite, infanzie e altri miracoli. Letture apocrife fra Oriente e Occidente* (Armarium 19), Rubettino, Soveria Mannelli 2023 for **VI Festival di Antropologia e Storia delle Religioni “Nella Terra di Diana”**, Roma – Genzano di Roma, 5th – 8th September 2024;
- 3.6. **2024:** 6th September, **Genzano di Roma (RM):** conference with Rossana Barcellona and Antonio Mursia on the book of E.N. Barile, N. Gadaleta, M. Resta (a cura di), *Fede, cultura e pellegrinaggi tra Atlantico e Mediterraneo. Da Finisterre a Santa Maria di Leuca de finibus terrae* (Bibliotheca Michaelica 11), Edipuglia, Bari 2022 for **VI Festival di Antropologia e Storia delle Religioni “Nella Terra di Diana”**, Roma – Genzano di Roma, 5th – 8th September 2024;
- 3.7. **2023:** 13th December, **Erfurt (DE):** «Case studies of divine property between 4th and 6th century: from the Lateran to the *tituli* of Rome, from donations to testaments in the Latin World» for **SFB Seminar (colloquia) Series on “Structural Change of Property”, subproject A01 “Divine Property. Solutions from Late Antiquity and the Middle Ages”** of the *Max-Weber-Kolleg* of **University of Erfurt**, Erfurt 20th October 2023 – 6th February 2024;
- 3.8. **2023:** 10th September, **Ariccia (RM):** conference with Tessa Canella and Marco Papisidero on the book of M. Papisidero, M. Resta (eds.), *I santi internauti 2. Agiografia, devozioni e icone digitali* (Sanctorum. Scritture, pratiche, immagini 10), Viella, Roma 2022 for **V Festival di Antropologia e Storia delle Religioni “Nella Terra di Diana”**, Ariccia, 7th -10th September 2023;
- 3.9. **2023:** 20th June, **St. Andrews, UK:** «Christians Dancing for the Martyrs in Late Antiquity» for the panel on «Death According to the Abrahamic Religions Between Late Antiquity and Early Modern Age» of the **Annual Conference** (6th edition) of the **European Academy of Religion (EuARe)** on «Religion from the Inside» (St. Andrews, 19th-23rd June 2023);
- 3.10. **2023:** 8th May, **Torino, Italy,** conference with Natale Spineto on the book «*Cristo vale meno di un ballerino?*». *Danza e musica strumentale nel vissuto dei cristiani di età tardoantica* (Edipuglia, Bari 2021) for **Seminar Series “I lunedì della Peterson”**;

- 3.11. **2023:** 14th February, **Bari, Italy:** «Da attori a santi: Gelasino e Ardalione, casi di martirio a confronto», **Seminar Series “Nuovi itinerari di Letteratura Cristiana Antica”**, organised by Consulta Universitaria di Letteratura Cristiana Antica (CULCA);
- 3.12. **2022:** 26th January, **Roma, Italy:** «La ‘santità’ secondo Achille Lauro tra TV e web», **Meeting “Cantieri dell’agiografia”**, 5th edition, Sapienza University of Roma, 26th – 28th January 2022;
- 3.13. **2021:** 29th September, **Bertinoro (FC), Italy:** «Lay or Consecrated, Subjected and Subtracted: The Abduction of Women in 4th Century Canonical Legislation», **7th International Annual Meeting on Christian Origins – online edition** (Bertinoro, 29th September – 2nd October 2021), organised by Mauro Pesce, Mara Rescio, Emiliano Rubens Urciuoli;
- 3.14. **2021:** 27th May, **Santa Maria Capua Vetere (CE), Italy:** «Popstar e santità: il caso di Achille Lauro», **Seminar Series “I santi internauti”**, University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”, Santa Maria Capua Vetere (CE) 8th April – 27th May 2021; link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O_fMrSKiGC8&list=PLkv7cij68iWhmDW9_SSA6nQV1kh-p51E&index=7;
- 3.15. **2020:** 7th December, **Bari, Italy:** «“La mia cetra accompagna i lamenti / e il mio flauto la voce di chi piange”: Gb 30,31 tra esegesi patristica e devozione medievale», **Seminar Series “Spiegare il dolore. Giobbe: un personaggio biblico e la sua ricezione tra giudaismo, cristianesimo e Islam”**, organised by Laura Carnevale (University of Bari, 16th November 2020 – 14th December 2020);
- 3.16. **2019:** 9th May, **Roma, Italy:** «Sul corpo delle donne: note su ratto e stupro nella legislazione canonica tardoantica», **XLVII Incontro di Studiosi dell’Antichità Cristiana:** «“Masculum et feminam creavit eos” (Gen. 1,27). Paradigmi del maschile e femminile nel cristianesimo antico» (Roma, 9th – 11th May 2019);
- 3.17. **2018:** 19th April, **Santa Maria Capua Vetere (CE), Italy:** «La battaglia di Ognissanti sul web: note sul fenomeno di Halloween in Italia», **International Meeting “I santi internauti. Esplorazioni agiografiche sul web”**, University of Campania “Luigi Vanvitelli”, 19th – 20th April 2018, organised by Claudia Santi e Daniele Solvi; link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tfRRTB9qRpk>;
- 3.18. **2018:** 17th January 2018, **Roma, Italy:** «Devozione mariana tra malattia e guarigione», **Meeting “Cantieri di agiografia”**, 2nd edition, Roma 17th – 18th January 2018;
- 3.19. **2017:** 15th June 2017, **Ravenna, Italy:** «I “balli” di san Vito: fonti, luoghi e riti del culto. Un’indagine storico-agiografica», **Workshop “Corpi danzanti dall’Antichità al Rinascimento”**, Alma Mater Studiorum University of Bologna 15th – 16th June 2017, organised by Luigi Canetti e Nicoletta Guidobaldi;
- 3.20. **2017:** 24th May 2017, **Bari, Italy:** «I “balli” di san Vito: fonti, luoghi e riti del culto nell’Italia meridionale», **International Meeting “Spazi sacri. Espressioni ed esperienze del vissuto religioso”**, University of Bari, 23rd – 25th May 2017.

4. TEACHING

- 4.1. **2025:** 21st October, h: 8,10 - 9,50, lecture on «La letteratura subapostolica», as part of the **History of Christianity teaching** for the **Bachelor' degree courses** of the Department of Research and Innovation in Humanities of University of Bari Aldo Moro (ref.: prof. Immacolata Aulisa);
- 4.2. **2025:** 20th October, h: 11,30 - 13,10, lecture on «I Vangeli apocrifi dell'infanzia: il Protovangelo di Giacomo», as part of the **History of Christianity teaching** for the **Master's degree courses** of Department of Research and Innovation in Humanities of University of Bari Aldo Moro (ref.: prof. Immacolata Aulisa);
- 4.3. **2024:** 4th December, h: 11.30 - 13.10, lecture on “I vangeli apocrifi dell'infanzia: il Protovangelo di Giacomo”, as part of the **History of Christianity teaching** for the **Master's degree courses** of Department of Research and Innovation in Humanities of University of Bari Aldo Moro (ref.: prof. Immacolata Aulisa);
- 4.4. **2024:** 7th November, h: 8.10 - 9.50, lecture on “La letteratura apologetica”, as part of the **History of Christianity teaching** for the **Bachelor' degree courses** of the Department of Research and Innovation in Humanities of University of Bari Aldo Moro (ref.: prof. Immacolata Aulisa);
- 4.5. **2024:** 5th November, h: 8,10 - 9,50, lecture on “Ognissanti vs Halloween: origini storiche di un conflitto reale e virtuale in Italia”, as part of **History of Christianity teaching** for the **Bachelor' degree courses** of the Department of Research and Innovation in Humanities of University of Bari Aldo Moro (ref.: prof. Immacolata Aulisa);
- 4.6. **2024:** 4th November, h: 11,30 - 13,10, lecture on “Ognissanti vs Halloween: origini storiche di un conflitto reale e virtuale in Italia”, as part of **History of Christianity teaching** for the **Master's degree courses** of Department of Research and Innovation in Humanities of University of Bari Aldo Moro (ref.: prof. Immacolata Aulisa);
- 4.7. **2022:** 31st May, h: 11-12, seminar on “Negare il diritto alla libertà: il ratto e lo stupro delle donne nelle legislazione canonica tardoantica” for **PhD students of Doctoral School in Humanities** (University of Bari), Seminar Series “Ripensare la ‘natura umana’. Paradigmi interpretativi ed emergenze storiche”
- 4.8. **2020:** 13th May, h: 16,30-18, seminar on “I ‘balli’ di san Vito: pratiche e riti coreutico-culturali euromediterranei” for **PhD students of Doctoral School in Humanities** (University of Bari), Seminar Series “Itinerari e identità nel Mediterraneo antico: cultura, politica, comunicazione”.

5. PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT AND KNOWLEDGE DISSEMINATION

- 5.1. **2025:** 20th December, Monte Sant'Angelo (FG): speaker at the seminar on “I luoghi sacri dell'Arcangelo Michele nel Sud Italia”, organised by Centro di Studi Micaelici e Garganici “Giorgio Otranto” dell'Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro and Associazione “Monte Sant'Angelo Francigena”. Title of the presentation: «Il culto di san Michele in Oriente».

- 5.2. **2025:** 7th March, Bari: speaker at the training seminar for tourist guides and tour leaders, organised by Federagit Metropolitana Terra di Bari. Title of the presentation: «Ballare per i santi: il caso di san Vito tra Europa e Mediterraneo»;
- 5.3. **2024:** 30th November, Giovinazzo (BA), chair for the presentation of the book of F. Panarelli, *Dante a Mezzogiorno. Il Regno di Sicilia nella Commedia*, Carocci, Roma 2024 (speakers: Francesco Panarelli, Francesco Violante), organised by the Gruppo FAI del Nord Barese;
- 5.4. **2023:** 30th December, interview by Valerio Castrignano on “Fax Polignano”: *San Vito, la taranta è roba nostra* (p. 21);
- 5.5. **2023:** 20th July, Bitonto (BA): conference with Andrea Maraschi for “Sapericena. Cultura a piccoli morsi”; presentation on: «Un banchetto per danzare, ridere, morire»;
- 5.6. **2023:** 29th June, educational kit on “Santità e web” with Marco Papasidero for PARS (Portale di formazione e informazione per il contrasto dell’analfabetismo religioso): <https://pars-edu.it/visualizza-percorso-formativo/nojs/3682/0>;
- 5.7. **2023:** 16th June, Laterza (TA): conference for restoration of St. Vitus canvas painting (*Mater Domini* Sanctuary); presentation on: «Dall’esorcismo ai ‘balli’ di san Vito»;
- 5.8. **2021:** 13th June, interview on *Letture.org* about the book «*Cristo vale meno di un ballerino?*». *Danza e musica strumentale nel vissuto dei cristiani di età tardoantica*, Edipuglia, Bari 2021: <https://www.letture.org/cristo-vale-meno-di-un-ballerino-danza-e-musica-strumentale-nel-vissuto-dei-cristiani-di-eta-tardoantica-mario-resta/>;
- 5.9. **2021:** 4th June, radio presentation (www.usmaradio.org) with Caterina Ciccopiedi and Alfredo Ferrara of the book of Francesca De Robertis, *I documenti sulla morte di Giordano Bruno*, Il Mulino, Bologna 2021; event organised with the Department of History and the High School of Historical Studies of the University of the Republic of San Marino;
- 5.10. **2020:** 21st December, conference with Fabio Frisino on the Facebook Group “Kairos – Storia del cristianesimo”; chair: Alessandro Turano; presentation on: *Danza: possessione, malattia e cura. Dal ballo di san Vito al tarantismo*; link FB: <https://fb.watch/2D8coerQST/>; link YouTube: https://youtu.be/eQ_rKtnLJZc;
- 5.11. **2020:** 28th November, conference on Facebook Page “La storia degli storici”; chair: Edoardo Furiesi; presentation on: *Ognissanti vs Halloween: note sulle origini storiche di un conflitto reale e virtuale in Italia*; link FB: <https://fb.me/e/1DRf0C0Vj>; <https://fb.watch/26ibvIIBAU/>; link YouTube: <https://youtu.be/DXu9NVIgbPU>;
- 5.12. **2019:** 4th July, interview by Giuseppe Fraccalvieri on “ClassiCult.it”: *Giobbe patrono dei musicisti: intervista a Mario Resta*; link: <http://www.classicult.it/giobbe-patrono-dei-musicisti-intervista-a-mario-resta/>